

**CYBERCRIME AND LAW ENFORCEMENT: JURISDICTIONAL CHALLENGES IN
THE DIGITAL ERA (PAKISTAN)**

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ABSTRACT

Cybercrime has quickly become one of the most complicated areas of focus of law enforcement in Pakistan. With the growth of digital communication, there is increased criminal exploitation. This article focuses on the role played by law enforcement institutions in Pakistan especially the Federal Investigation Agency (FIA) and its recent replacement, the National Cyber Crime Investigation Agency (NCCIA) in curbing the rising issue of cybercrime in complex jurisdictional frameworks. The paper identifies overlapping legal jurisdiction, technological and international cooperation constraints as a problem. Particular recognition is given to Supervisor whose advice and encouragement was key in forming the direction of the research and analytical profundity of this work. (Khan & Zia, 2021) (Ahmed, 2023).

INTRODUCTION

Technology has now dominated the way people talk, purchase, work, and even the manner in which the government services operate. Due to this, cybercrime is posing a serious threat. Cybercrime reflects identity theft, Internet scam, Internet harassment, and computer terrorism. Such offences have the potential of jeopardizing personal privacy and national security. This is a problem that is increasing rapidly in Pakistan. The problem is that law enforcement is usually lagging behind as laws and policing system have very few changes to suit the modern crime-fighting issues. (Khan & Zia, 2021).

In Pakistan, the police at the level of ordinary work play a significant, yet the limited role in cybercrime cases. They do even their work which in this case is conventional crime like theft, assault, fraud and public order. Online threats or harassment might be reported on police stations. However, not every police group has sufficient training on digital investigation. They do not also have digital evidence gathering and analyzing tools. As an illustration, the forensic laboratory at Quetta (near traffic office), Spinni Road lacks modern technology necessary in robust cybercrime investigation. (Khan & Zia, 2021).

The Prevention of Electronic Crimes Act (PECA) 2016 has made the Federal Investigation Agency (FIA) a Cybercrime investigator. The Cyber Crime Wing of the FIA was to investigate online offences, collect digital evidence and collaborate with other nations where necessary. Nevertheless, cyber threats are more sophisticated and frequent. As a result of this, the government came up with a significant reform and established the National Cyber Crime Investigation Agency (NCCIA) in 2023. NCCIA is a different federal agency that only addresses cybercrime. It would like to possess specialized personnel, better digital laboratories, and become more autonomous. (Khan & Zia, 2021) (Ahmed, 2023).

This shift is an indication of improvement of the cyber law enforcement system in Pakistan. But it raises new issues as well. These are lack of clarity of jurisdiction, poor coordination and legal overlap among the agencies. The two issues are the subject of this research.

Inter-Jurisdictional Cooperation Among Police and the Role of CrPC, NCCIA, and PECA (Khan & Zia, 2021) (Ahmed, 2023)

In Pakistan, the cross-jurisdictional cooperation between the police forces is primarily governed by the Code of Criminal Procedure (CrPC) 1898 that defines how the country investigates and prosecutes criminals. Under Sections 154 to 176 of the CrPC (Code of Criminal Procedure 1898), any police station within which information is received regarding an offense is required to file a First Information Report (FIR) and institute an enquiry or investigation. But in cases where the offense is related to more than one jurisdiction, for example, a cyber fraud is committed in one province to a victim in another, and Section 182 and 183 of the CrPC (Code of Criminal Procedure 1898) permit inter-jurisdictional collaboration that officers in one district or province may cooperate or turn over the investigation to the qualified authority. Traditionally, this coordination has been conducted through written channels and intergovernmental cooperation between Station House Officers (SHOs) of the concerned police stations.

In the realm of cybercrime, however, jurisdiction becomes more complicated due to the borderless nature of digital offenses. To address this, the Prevention of Electronic Crimes Act (PECA) 2016 introduced a new legal domain, giving investigative powers to the Federal Investigation Agency (FIA) under Section 29. With the recent amendment of 2023, the powers have

officially been delegated to the National Cyber Crime Investigation Agency (NCCIA), which has since become the central federal agency responsible with cyber related investigations. The Schedule accompanying PECA Act over time with the government notification obviously outlines what kind of offences are subject to NCCIA jurisdiction such as unauthorized access, stealing information, cyber terrorism, harassment on the internet, and online fraud. Provincial or local police may still institute an initial complaint under CrPC Section 154 but must refer it to the NCCIA to have it investigated by a specialist where the offense is subject to the PECA schedule. (Khan & Zia, 2021) (Ahmed, 2023).

In reality, collaboration between the provincial police and NCCIA has a designed hierarchy. Local law enforcements verify preliminary complaints and keep evidence, NCCIA officers complete digital forensic, IP address tracing, and liaise with internet service providers or foreign agencies. The CrPC is therefore the procedural platform of communication, warrants and evidence delivery, but the operational framework of the NCCIA provides that cyber investigations are technically and legally accurate. This coordinated practice is designed to avoid redundancy, make electronic evidence admissible, and boost the effectiveness of Pakistan in responding to interjurisdictional crimes. (Ahmed, 2023).

Resolution of Jurisdictional Disputes Between Police and NCCIA (Ahmed, 2023)

When questions arise over which authority provincial police or the National Cyber Crime Investigation Agency (NCCIA) is competent to investigate a particular offense, Pakistani law provides both procedural and administrative mechanisms to resolve the issue. Under Section 36 of the Code of Criminal Procedure (CrPC), superior officers of police have the power to direct or supervise investigations within their jurisdiction, and by extension, may communicate with federal agencies to avoid Repetitive investigation efforts. In cybercrime cases, however, Section 29 of the Prevention of Electronic Crimes Act (PECA) 2016 explicitly gives the federal government, through the Ministry of Interior, the power to designate the investigating agency. This means that if a case involves digital evidence, cross-border servers, or offenses listed in the Schedule of PECA such as unauthorized access, cyber terrorism, or electronic fraud the NCCIA automatically assumes primary jurisdiction. (Khan & Zia, 2021) (Ahmed, 2023).

Conflict general emerges when a cyber related offense also includes elements of conventional crime (for example, blackmail, extortion, or defamation). In such hybrid cases, coordination committees often chaired by the District Public Prosecutor or a Judicial Magistrate help determine which agency should lead. The police may continue to handle physical evidence and local witness examination, while NCCIA investigators deal with digital forensics and network tracing. Functional competence is its guiding principle, where each agency does the task of the investigation best suited to their specialization. In case of the ambiguity of jurisdiction, the responsibility is allocated to the Federal Government, which can provide a formal notification in accordance with Rule 4 of PECA Investigation Rules (2023 Amendment). (Khan & Zia, 2021) (Ahmed, 2023).

Practically, this structure creates a collaborative atmosphere where police agencies exchange information, coordinate warrants and the chain of command is observed. Despite the administrative bottlenecks that persist writing Committee PECA and the procedural safeguards found in CrPC have already led to a more methodical approach to digital crime investigations. The current partnership of the NCCIA and provincial police, therefore, constitutes the attempt of Pakistan to reconcile conventional police and new cyber governance whereby justice is neither geographically constrained nor institutionalized in outdated formats. (Khan & Zia, 2021) (Ahmed, 2023).

Transition to Judicial Perspective

The connection between the Code of criminal Procedure (CrPC) and the Prevention of Electronic Crimes Act (PECA) and the establishment of the National Cyber Crime Investigation Agency (NCCIA) indicate that Pakistan is becoming better in responding towards cybercrime. These legislations give minimal guidelines on how agencies are to be coordinated. But practically, they are frequently left to the interpretation of courts. A major role in cybercrime is played by the judiciary. Courts assist in demystification of uncertain jurisdiction amongst agencies. They are also required to make the process of digital evidence collection lawful. Besides, they safeguard constitutional rights also considering the needs of national security. In this study, the views of a Judicial Magistrate have been incorporated to observe the operation of these legal rules in actual investigations. The experience of the Magistrate is used to clarify issues of the day to day procedures. It also brings out issues of handling digital evidence. Lastly, it presents loopholes that persist in institutions and the prosecution of cybercrimes cases in Pakistan. (Khan & Zia, 2021) (Ahmed, 2023).

Problem Statement

Cybercrime in Pakistan has been increasing, at a high rate and the response instituted by governmental bodies has not happened in the same manner. The conventional policing is founded on the borders and daily law-and-order tasks. Conversely, cybercrimes tend to cut across localities, provinces, and even national boundaries. This gives a sharp dislocation between cybercrime and the boundaries of jurisdiction of local police. The Criminal Procedure Code (CrPC) specifies the powers and procedures of investigation but is not entirely meant to address complicated digital offenses. Most cyber cases have multi jurisdictions and demand high-tech digital forensics. They also require close interdepartmental and interagency coordination. (Khan & Zia, 2021).

As per the Prevention of Electronic Crimes Act (PECA), the Federal Investigation Agency (FIA) has the mandate to probe some of the cybercrimes. However, its specialized mandate usually conflicts with provincial police cyber units. This overlap may result in confusion on whether or not a case should be handled by someone. In most cases, victims initiate cyber-related cases by reporting to the local police stations. There is a shortage of technical skills and clear standard procedures by many of the officers. They can also lack knowledge regarding the legal provisions on jurisdiction. This means that they would be in the dark as to whether to remain with the local police or be sent to FIA or the National Cyber Crime Investigation Agency (NCCIA). This unproductiveness can lead to procrastination. It also may cause poor management of complaints and practice of unequal law enforcement. (Khan & Zia, 2021) (Ahmed, 2023).

Agencies have poor communication channels. Inter-jurisdiction cooperation is also less. Various units do not have digital investigation tools and resources. Such problems lessen the effectiveness with which cybercrime is enforced. Cybercrime is also getting advanced. It has now incorporated financial fraud, identity theft, online harassment and digital extortion. With the increasing threat, the difference between the legal obligation and the real ability is established even more distinctly. Due to such weaknesses, victims experience confusion in procedures. They also receive delayed reactions. This decreases the confidence of the people in the police. The first issue is that there is no clear and coordinated system. Pakistan must also have a system that facilitates cross-police jurisdictions. It also requires skilled personnel and good technological capability in dedicated cyber agencies. (Khan & Zia, 2021) (Khalid, 2020).

Discussion

The difficulties of applying cyber laws in Pakistan becomes obvious when considering the actual law enforcement situations. Interview with a Judicial Magistrate VII (Kachari, Quetta), FIA officer

and with the NCCIA officer proved a good idea to understand the way the cases of the cybercrime are handled in the judicial system. (Khan & Zia, 2021) (Ahmed, 2023).

The Magistrate wrote that the process delay occurs when deciding on jurisdiction. The fact that, cyber offenses frequently cut across borders and even nations makes it controversial as to which court or agency is in control. As an example, when a cyber fraud has its origin in Quatta and impact to a victim in Islamabad, local police might have to forward the issue to FIA (or more recently NCCIA) but can result in a lengthy and slow process. (Ahmed, 2023) (Khan & Zia, 2021).

The other important point of debate was the issue of privacy of data and sovereignty in the digital world. The courts of Pakistan have already started struggling with the problems of receiving information stored in foreign servers (on Facebook or Google) where the Mutual Legal Assistance Treaties (MLATs) are necessary. The processes are however, time consuming and anyone involved in crime tends to take advantage of this time lag.

The Magistrate concluded that the future of cybercrime policing in Pakistan lies in coordinated digital governance that will fill the gaps between the judiciary, police, and the special agencies with technology and legal change. (Khan & Zia, 2021).

Discussion with a Judicial Magistrate (Mr. Israr Ullah)

In order to obtain a ground-level view of how cybercrime cases are managed through the Pakistani legal system, a close discussion was had with a Judicial Magistrate working as a Special Magistrate of FIA in Kachari Quetta. The Magistrate pointed out that cybercrime is a special group of crimes in which conventional investigative tools do not always serve the requirements of digital evidence gathering, travel costs and geographic organization. Cybercrimes do not respect geographical limits, unlike physical crimes where the area is defined thus necessitating the coordination of several agencies, courts and even international stakeholders. (Khan & Zia, 2021).

The Magistrate further noted that the Code of Criminal Procedure (CrPC) is the procedural basis of a full-fledged investigation, yet it was created based on classical types of crimes and lacks the inherent flexibility required to solve modern digital cases. The Magistrate also clarified that the Prevention of Electronic Crimes Act (PECA) 2016 is the main substantive law in cybercrime cases, and the NCCIA acts as the investigative agency specializing in cybercrimes. The Magistrate observed that cases under the First Schedule of PECA; those involving online fraud, data breaches, identity thefts and cyber harassment, need to be sent to the NCCIA, despite the original complaint being lodged at a local police station. This assures that the evidence is manipulated by qualified digital forensic specialists who keep it admissible under the Qanoon-e-Shahadat Order 1984 (the law of evidence in Pakistan). (Khan & Zia, 2021) (Ahmed, 2023).

The Magistrate did admit, however, that procedural delays and jurisdictional issues are significant impediments. In a number of cases local police have begun to investigate online fraud or harassment without understanding that such incidents are within the NCCIA jurisdiction. In saying that, when there are such cases, the court is forced to step in and usually instruct the case to be reallocated to the relevant agency. The Magistrate emphasized that such an operation can create weeks of delay time during which digital evidence of any value can be lost or damaged. To mitigate this, courts gradually advance collective investigative procedures, where law enforcement officers serve initial functions such as the recording of complaints and detention of suspects, whereas NCCIA officers perform the forensic and technical part of the investigation. (Ahmed, 2023).

The Magistrate also stressed the need to be judicially aware and capacity building. Most trial judges, even in lower courts, are still learning the technical side of digital evidence learning the IP traces,

data logs, or blockchain transactions. Training sessions and workshops, which are in most cases being undertaken in conjunction with the Federal Judicial Academy and NCCIA, are slowly enhancing judiciary capacity to assess electronic evidence. The Magistrate emphasized that the success of a justice system during the digital era is characterized by intense cooperation between the investigators, prosecutors, and judges, which should be backed by recent amendments in the legal system and timely information sharing between different agencies. (Ahmed, 2023).

Summing up, it was seen that although the judiciary in Pakistan appreciates the steps taken by building the NCCIA and perfecting cyber laws under PECA, much integration of procedures is yet to be done. What the Magistrate has to say reiterates the need to have an integrated, technology-focused operation to prosecute cybercrime one capable of integrating the procedural power of the CrPC and the cybercrime expertise of the NCCIA so that justice is not just delivered but retained. with the evolving digital landscape. (Khan & Zia, 2021) (Ahmed, 2023).

Discussion with an FIA Cybercrime Officer (Khan & Zia, 2021).

In an in-depth interview with a FIA officer who has been in charge of various cyberspace crime cases, some operational issues have become obvious. The officer stressed that the time spent on cybercrime cases is greatly conditioned by the difficulty with the collection of digital evidence. Contrasting with the methods of traditional investigations, where the evidence is physically restricted to a crime scene, cybercrime evidence can simultaneously be located on multiple devices, web applications, and remote servers. Every one of the steps, asking subscribers to provide information, obtaining server logs, acquiring metadata, or obtaining content of social media companies, needs some formal procedures and legal paperwork. Due to it, even cases that seem straightforward initially might require a few weeks, whereas more complicated ones like financial transactions, cyber-extortion, or cross-border data trails might take months. (Khan & Zia, 2021).

The officer further clarified that these timelines are further extended under the jurisdictional constraints. Even though PECA, FIA has the federal investigative authority, there are numerous aspects of its operation that need the coordination with provincial and district-level police. In situations where suspects are located somewhere FIA finds it inaccessible, they are forced to use the assistance of the local police to perform their searches, seizures of equipment, and obtain the testimony. Such inter-agency coordination is not always smooth. Information getting stuck due to administrative back logs, misperception of procedures, and lack of uniform communication channels often become obstacles in the promptness of investigative action. (Khan & Zia, 2021).

The lack of operational funding was also another major problem that appeared in the discussion. According to the officer, the realities of fieldwork are usually a challenge to the cybercrime teams. In some cases where a suspect is far away other than the regional FIA office, investigators are not able to travel instantly because of their limited travel allowances and rigid budget approval provisions. On-ground searching, seizure of devices, interviews with witnesses, field visits are usually postponed pending approval of funds. These delays may allow evidence manipulation or device destruction which undermines cases in instances that the suspects stay in isolated districts. (Khan & Zia, 2021).

In general, the officer emphasized that, although investigators have good technical skills, structural and logistical constraints constitute a major factor influencing the effectiveness of cybercrime investigations. Better budgetary allocations, autonomous mobility resources and a leaner inter-jurisdictional system would significantly improve the responsiveness of cybercrime units. The discussion has highlighted the necessity to enhance institutional amenity to cope with the growing complexity and cases of cybercrime in Pakistan. (Khan & Zia, 2021).

Discussion with an NICCA Cybercrime Officer

An in-depth interview with the FIA cybercrime officer on the subject matter discovered some important details about the realities of the cybercrime investigation in Pakistan. The officer represented the increasing sophistication of evidence collection and the institutional limitation of investigative times on the collection of electronic crimes under the Prevention of Electronic Crimes Act (PECA) in which he has had long-standing experience in crime prevention. His view gives a practicable experience of the way cybercrime is handled on a working level and how different administrative and logistic factors influence the effectiveness of investigators. (Khan & Zia, 2021).

The officer started by stating that the cases related to cybercrime are determined mostly by the type of digital evidence that is presented. This is unlike conventional types of crime where evidence is usually limited to a physical crime site but in cybercrime, evidence is available in intangible, decentralized and often volatile forms. This consists of IP logs, communication logs, financial transaction logs, mobile data, cloud storage data and metadata of many applications. The officer added that every type of data needs formal approval and undergoes a sequence of procedural processes to be acquired. Orders to telecom companies, such as, should be in rigid legal formats and normally require days to be executed. When law enforcement officers require the services of foreign sites like Facebook, WhatsApp, or Google, the timescale grows significantly as these corporations demand legitimate access orders based on international data-sharing conditions. Even minor issues, like a case of harassment, identity theft, account hacking, or blackmailing done electronically, can require weeks to resolve just because the investigators have to wait to the services to answer an official request of the data. (Khan & Zia, 2021).

The officer continued by explaining that the high profile cases or technically involved cases normally last several months. Offenses related to digital financial fraud, cryptocurrency exchanges, or ransomware must be analyzed and coordinated with foreign cooperation. The devices in such cases can have encrypted files, deleted files or failed partitions that need to be extracted cautiously to preserve the integrity of the evidence. The officer emphasized that investigators have to take a hard chain of custody throughout the process as any gap in procedures will make digital evidence inadmissible in court. These procedural and technical requirements cause major extensions of the time frame of the investigation and demand considerable interdisciplinary collaboration of digital forensic laboratories, legal personnel, and investigative divisions.

The jurisdictional barriers as a factor that is influential on case progress were also brought up in the discussion. The FIA is given federal powers to probe cybercrime, but in on-ground cases the support of local police is usually needed. This is particularly difficult in cases where the suspects are in remote districts or provinces. According to the officer, FIA teams have no right to operate at will outside the regional offices, without informing and coordinating with local police teams. In most scenarios, a formal communication procedure has to be performed prior to any form of investigative process, which includes raids, arrests, seizure of devices. Though coordination would be required it is not necessarily efficiency. There are often administrative bottlenecks, poor jurisdictional roles or interdepartmental lags that achieve delay. These problems are magnified in those cases when it involves more than one province where they need authorization of additional permissions, logistical organization, and even negotiation with different local units. (Khan & Zia, 2021).

The officer underlined that insufficient operational funds could be considered one of the most frequent issues with timely investigations. Cybercrime teams usually enjoy limited budgets with travel budgets being very minimal. When suspects are distant with the area authorities, the investigators cannot promptly send teams on the ground because they have to seek authorization to travel, prepare vehicles, and budget on accommodation. The officer observed that investigations

often do not go anywhere due to the fact that before field teams go to gather devices, interview witnesses, or secure crime scenes, they have to wait financial approvals. These administrative limitations get even greater in remote or in rural settings, where teams are unable to act quickly in response to them (Interior Baluchistan, Interior Sindh, Interior Peshawar). The officer admitted that the lapse of time due to lack of funds can compromise integrity of investigations, particularly in those cases where suspects might manipulate digital evidence or move the devices before team members arrive at the scene.

Besides the shortages of funds, the officer also indicated inter-agency integration gaps. Cyber investigators can use external sources to carry out some sections of the investigation process e.g. multi-language digital content verification at a specialized lab, certified translation, etc. These support services might also be constrained in terms of resources and therefore, their schedule also adds the total lifespan of the case. The officer said that having a centralized national database of cybercrime suspects, repeat cases or heavily used IP infrastructures would be highly beneficial to the speed of investigations. A lack of such systems is not yet standardized, and investigators must collect and verify data by hand it is a time-consuming task. (Khan & Zia, 2021).

Even face to face these issues, the officer asserted that the FIA cybercrime units have good technical capacities and constantly adjusting themselves with new methodologies. He claimed that the only way to improve the general efficiency of responding to cybercrime is by enhancing structural and logistical assistance. Dedicated resource allocation toward mobility, the growth of forensic labs, acceleration of inter-agency reporting systems, and better jurisdiction would help delay considerably. He further added that a more integrated and responsive cyber-enforcement system by boosting the level of coordination between FIA and the provincial police forces, accompanied by joint training programs, common databases, and standardized digital evidence practices. (Khan & Zia, 2021).

On the whole, the discussion highlights the fact that although cybercrime investigations require high technical competence, they also require administrative efficiency and access to resources. The experiences of the FIA officer demonstrate that the investigative climate is shaped by various factors such as delays in terms of evidence collection, the lack of jurisdiction, and insufficient funds. It is critical that these structural gaps be addressed to not only enhance institutional performance but also boost the level of trust that people have in the country to effectively fight cybercrime. (Khan & Zia, 2021).

CONCLUSION

The transformation of the traditional policing to the digital policing in Pakistan can be associated with both improvements and limitations in development. The creation of the NCCIA is a landmark step in acknowledging cybercrime as a unique and multifaceted threat that has to be addressed specifically. Jurisdictional problem exists not only between the police, FIA, and NCCIA but also within the judicial process itself. (Khan & Zia, 2021) (Ahmed, 2023) (Siddiqui, 2022)

To strengthen cybercrime enforcement, Pakistan must: (Khan & Zia, 2021).

- Clearly define jurisdictional authority between national and provincial bodies.
- Enhance digital forensic training for law enforcement.
- Improve judicial awareness regarding electronic evidence.
- Develop bilateral cooperation for cross-border data sharing.
- Rules for Legally admissible electronic evidence.

Conclusively good cyber governance will be based on integrating the technology innovation and sound legal frameworks. It is only at that point when Pakistan will be able to protect its digital citizens in the rapidly changing cyber world.

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